

OPTIMIZING SOD IN ERP: A FRAMEWORK ENHANCING MANUAL REVIEWS WITH PROCESS MINING

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Keywords Business Process, Segregation of Duties (SoD), Process Mining, Role Mining Entire Resources Planning (ERP) Automatic Review - Risk Finding, Authorization Matrix, Risk violations, Conformance Matrix.

Abstract: Segregation of Duties (SoD) is a critical internal control principle in Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems like SAP. Traditional methods rely on manual reviews of static documentation, which can be time-consuming and error-prone due to the large volume of data and the complexity of ERP systems. This paper proposes a novel framework that combines manual reviews with process mining to enhance SoD compliance in ERP systems. The framework leverages process mining tools to analyze user activity data and identify potential SoD violations based on a pre-defined SoD policy and matrix. Manual reviews are then employed to assess the context and risk associated with identified violations. This combined approach offers several benefits, including improved efficiency, accuracy, and continuous monitoring of SoD compliance. The paper outlines the framework's components, its benefits, and its contribution to strengthening internal controls within ERP systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Segregation of Duties (SoD) is a fundamental internal control principle that safeguards organizations against fraudulent activities within Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems like SAP. It dictates that incompatible tasks within a business process should not be performed by the same user, mitigating the risk of unauthorized access, manipulation, or misuse of sensitive data. Traditionally, ensuring SoD compliance involves manual reviews of process documentation and user access controls. However, this approach has limitations.

Firstly, relying solely on static documentation can be ineffective, as documented processes may not always reflect actual workflows. Secondly, manual reviews are time-consuming, resource-intensive, and susceptible to human error, especially in complex ERP systems with numerous users and intricate access controls.

To address these limitations, this paper proposes a novel framework that combines the strengths of manual reviews with the power of process mining for a more robust and efficient SoD implementation within ERP systems. Process mining is a data-driven technique that utilizes event logs captured by IT systems to reconstruct and analyze actual process execution. By leveraging process mining, the proposed framework can automate the detection of potential SoD violations based on a pre-defined SoD policy and matrix. This paper delves into the details of this framework, outlining its components, its advantages over traditional methods, and its contribution to enhancing SoD compliance and internal control effectiveness within ERP environments.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Segregation of Duties (SoD) remains a cornerstone of internal control frameworks within Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems. While its importance is well established, research highlights limitations in traditional implementation methods. This literature review explores existing research on SoD in ERP systems and the potential of process mining to address these limitations.

There are three main models for SoD: Agency theory model: This model focuses on collusion between employees and supervisors. It suggests segregating custody of assets from decision-making and independent review. Practitioner model: This model focuses on preventing embezzlement. It suggests segregating custody of assets from authorization and recording of transactions. Business process model: This model reflects how SoD is implemented in organizations. It may not always strictly follow the other two models.[1]

A segregation of duties (SoD) policy is essential for IT managers to ensure data security, compliance, and operational resilience. It creates a framework to reduce risks by dividing tasks among different people. This is no longer optional but a strategic necessity, especially for complex organizations with various regulations. By following SoD, IT managers can improve their overall security posture. Dynamic SoD policy review is crucial for organizations changing. It ensures SoD rulesets adapt to new applications and business processes transformational changes, keeping your policies relevant and effective. [2]

Moss Adams. (2018) mentioned the importance of internal controls to prevent fraud and ensure compliance. Segregation of duties is a key principle where critical tasks are divided among multiple people or departments to reduce risk. The author offers to help improve your organization's internal controls and comply with regulations.[3]

Organizations can suffer reputational damage and financial loss from fraud and errors. This can be prevented by implementing strong internal controls, which involve dividing critical tasks among different people or departments (segregation of duties). Julia Mundy, and Carys A. Owen 2013 explain how proper risk management and internal controls can help your business comply with regulations like Sarbanes-Oxley (SOX).[4] The study found that ERP systems can address weaknesses in internal controls identified in previous research. These weaknesses were in areas like segregation of duties and account reconciliation and could lead to penalties. The author showed that ERP systems can significantly improve SOX compliance in these areas. This highlights the important role technology plays in supporting financial management and regulatory compliance.[4]

Al-Ahmadi, S., & Rezgui, Y. (2020) proposes a framework for business process risk assessment that incorporates process mining, but it can be adapted to the context of SoD analysis in ERPs. Also discusses a risk assessment methodology based on fuzzy logic for risks in the automotive domain. The proposed methodology offers several advantages, including increased granularity of risk values, easy handling by humans, and preservation of the linear ordering of calculated risks. The methodology is supported by automatic tools, making it practical and impactful.[5]

Lyu, J., Wang, J., & Li, J. (2021) discusses the limitations of current information security risk management frameworks in systematically identifying, analyzing, and evaluating threats. They propose a new hybrid model for information security risk assessment that integrates systematic threat analysis into IT risk management frameworks. The hybrid model is designed to complement existing practices and improve the precision of risk treatment planning by aligning technical security risk management with organizational practices. The model includes a sequence of core processes for risk identification, evaluation, and remediation, emphasizing the relationship between assets, vulnerabilities, threats, and countermeasures. Compare their model with existing standards and methodologies and present a case study to illustrate the typical implementation of risk management and the missing gap in threat analysis.[6]

A novel approach for fraud audit using visual analysis and process mining techniques aims to improve the detection of fraudulent activities in business processes. The approach involves a series of phases, including temporal analysis and exceptional pattern analysis, using techniques such as dotted chart visualizations and trace alignment to identify suspicious behaviors. The author presented a case study from the hospitality sector, where the approach successfully identified potentially fraudulent activities, such as operations on checks that exceeded normal customer service hours and unusual product deletion sequences.[7]

process mining tools offer the ability to check SoD in the event log, by applying constraints on the event log using the four-eyes principle and decreasing the power of an individual person or department in order to prevent fraud and errors, and the result will show matches cases with the applied constraints. However, the main input for the tool is event log which is the base of any process mining techniques. As it will discover the Fraud after happens. [8][9][10][11]

Celonis: A leading enterprise process mining platform that offers a variety of features for SoD analysis, including automated SoD rule detection, real-time process monitoring, and exception reporting [8]

AG ARIS Process Mining: This tool allows organizations to discover, analyze, and improve their business processes. It includes features for SoD analysis, helping organizations identify and mitigate risks associated with segregation of duties violations [9]

IBM Process Mining: Part of the IBM Cloud Pak for Business Automation suite, IBM Process Mining provides a comprehensive set of tools for process discovery, analysis, and improvement. It includes features for SoD analysis, helping organizations ensure compliance with internal controls [10]

UiPath: Offers a process mining capability within its Robotic Process Automation (RPA) platform. UiPath Process Mining helps identify SoD violations, analyze process variations, and optimize process efficiency.[11]

III. GAPS AND OPPORTUNITIES:

While traditional SoD implementation methods using manual reviews have served as a foundation for internal controls, there are significant gaps that limit their effectiveness in complex ERP systems. This framework will delve deeper into these limitations and explore how process mining offers opportunities to address them.

IV. LIMITATIONS OF TRADITIONAL MANUAL REVIEWS

- A. Time-Consuming and Resource-Intensive: Manually reviewing process documentation and user access controls for SoD compliance can be a tedious and lengthy process, especially in large organizations with extensive ERP systems. This can strain resources and limit the frequency of reviews.
- B. Inaccuracy and Incompleteness: Manual reviews rely on static documentation, which may not always reflect the actual workflows followed by users. Deviations from documented procedures or undocumented workarounds can easily go undetected, leaving SoD vulnerabilities exposed.

- C. Limited Scope of Analysis: Traditional methods often focus on reviewing pre-defined control points within a process. This narrow approach may miss more subtle SoD violations that emerge from the interplay of different activities within the broader workflow.
- D. Difficulty in Detecting Collusion: Manual reviews struggle to identify potential collusion between users with seemingly non-conflicting access rights. However, by working together, users can bypass SoD controls.

V. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

FIGURE 1

Proposed Framework

The framework is divided into three main components. Data Acquisition - Preparation, Automatic Review - Risk finding and Findings – Risk violations. This framework proposes a combined approach utilizing both automatic reviews and process mining for more robust and efficient implementation of SoD within Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, specifically focusing on SAP. This framework will provide a comprehensive approach to SoD in ERP systems, leveraging both technology and human expertise for a stronger internal control environment.

Definition 1 (Function) U_{tm} is a universe of transaction code t is used to run a program that can perform a certain action on the system. A function $f = \{t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, t_n\} \in U_{tm}$: - set of transaction codes and can be grouped to perform a function and can be classified as a critical function or SoD function

Definition 2 (Risk): - having access to a critical function or having access to more than one function should be segregated.

Can be defined as $RS(f) = [f(i) | f \in RS \wedge 1 \leq i \leq |f|]$

Definition 3 (SoDM): - a matrix mapping between functions to identify risks of having more than one function which may cause fraud or conflict of interest. And can be defined as $SoDM = (RS_1, RS_2, RS_3, \dots, RS_m)$

Definition 4 (Role): A Role $RL = \{t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, t_n\} \in U_{tm}$: - a set of transaction codes that can be grouped into a role and can be assigned to users and can be granted to multiple users.

Definition 5 (User Assignment): is the relation between user and role and can be defined as $UA_i = \{RL_1, RL_2, \dots, RL_n\}$

A. Data Acquisition – Preparation:

- SoD Policy and Matrix Definition:** the process of creating SoD depends on collaborating with stakeholders to define a clear SoD policy outlining incompatible activities within the ERP system. A detailed SoD matrix will explicitly identify these conflicting tasks and user roles that should not possess them. As shown in Figure 1 section A
- User Access definition:** granting access to the system user to perform a specific task within a process, thus, granting access to the user is not a direct relation between the user and the action (Program / Transaction code), as it must done through the user system role. A system role is a group of actions that can be granted to a group of users, and it may contain one action or more and can also be granted to one user or more. The same user can have access to one role or more than one role.
- User access Extraction:** as shown below in table 1, user access extraction can be done in three ways, first, extract from the authorization matrix (Role-based Access Control RBAC) to get users assigned to system roles, and get each transaction for each role, to have a list of transactions assigned to the user. This way provides real-time authorization review and is straightforward to review SoD, whoever it can't review changed authorization. Second by extraction from User Access Log UAL which contains for each user the accessed program and when, then by implementing role mining technique we can extract roles and user access list, secondly grouping user and access programs into roles based on access set. The output will be user access and role mining based on the event log this way will provide a SoD review for changed authorization however it can't provide proof of fraud. Third by extracting from the Process Event Log (PEL), which contains traces (case ID), activities, and users who performed this activity, and the date/time of execution then using role mining technique to get user access. Then by grouping the log based on user and activity, it will lead to a list of users linked with activities performed on the system. secondly grouping user and activity matrix into roles based on the activity set.

TABLE 1

Comparison between user access extraction source

User Access Extraction	Pros	Cons
RBAC	Easy to extract. Real-time authorization review	Can't review changed authorization
UAL	Easy to extract. Can review changed authorization	Can't prof fraud exist
PEL	Can review changed authorization. Prof fraud exists. (user executed not allowed actions in the same trace)	Hard to extract. Requires extracting from each E2E needs to be reviewed.

Role Mining – Algorithm.

Group log based on users / Activity.
 Group user/activity matrix into Roles based on User/activity set.
 Grouped activity set = Role mining
 Map user/activity matrix into user role assignment.

The output will be user access and role mining based on the event log. As shown in Figure 1 section A

Automatic Review - Risk finding – Algorithm.

Break SoD Matrix into Risk List
 Inner Join User Access with Risk List with {program, activity, transaction} = User Risk List
 Drop {program, activity, transaction} from the User Risk List.
 For each user in the list
 For each Risk in the Risk List
 If Risk Functions is a subset of the User Risk List,
 Then record user has risk.
 Else get the next Risk.

```

        End if.
    End for
End for

```

B. Automatic Review - Risk finding

Combining the SoD matrix and user access: by breaking down the SoD matrix into a risk function list and joining the risk function list with user access, a simple algorithm can be applied to find risks in user access. As shown in Figure 1 section B

Findings – Risk violations – Algorithm.

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Extract Process Event Log (EL)
For each user in the user risk list
    Select traces from EL.
    If an issue exists,
        Then record Fraud found.
    Else get next user.
End for

```

C. Findings – Risk violations

The output of automatic review – risk finding is a list of users who have risk. And can be validated for risk violations by applying a simple algorithm, however, it requires first getting the related event log of the end-to-end process (E2E) thus, by selecting user and risk functions, it can be validated by checking if the user has performed the actions within the same trace. As shown in Figure 1 section C

D. Remediation and Control Implementation:

Based on the risk assessment, determine appropriate remediation strategies for confirmed SoD violations.

This could involve:

1. User roles with conflicting activities.
2. Implementing mandatory approvals for specific transactions.
3. Restricting access to functionalities within existing roles.
4. Implementing additional technical controls like time-based access restrictions.

E. Continuous Monitoring and Improvement:

1. Regularly review user access and roles, especially after system changes or new user creations.
2. Utilize role mining for ongoing monitoring of SoD compliance and automatic review, allowing for early detection of potential violations.
3. Refine the SoD policy and matrix based on ongoing monitoring and identified risks.

VI. RESULTS

A. Authorization matrix and role mining

Table 2 authorization matrix agreed with stakeholders be applied, that no user is allowed to perform critical actions at the same time. It contains 57 actions with 663 risks.

Table 3 extracted data from the event log related to processing service orders. Which contains the service order number, action performed on the service order, date, time, and user who performed this action on this service order. The extracted is related to the end-to-end process for service order processing, for a month in Feb 2023 and contains 231'387 records of transactions with 39 actions performed by 154 users.

By applying the role mining technique in the framework, the output of the user action matrix is shown in Table 4, and the discovered roles are shown in Table 5.

B. Automatic Review - Risk finding

By applying automatic review of SoD on the user access log the output will be user has a risk to perform not authorized actions included in the SoD matrix, as shown in Table 6 User Risk List, has a user with risk and actions performed on the system. and by combining/summarizing the results, a conformance matrix shown in Table 7. Figure 2 shows user access time analysis, it will be useful to analyze user access as the results may show that the user has access to perform actions, however, due to management changes, it may be granted temporarily, in this case access, analysis by date will show the durations for each access.

TABLE 6

Results - User Risk List

User	Risk	Action
10906	ZCUST_SHOW	ZCUST_SHOW
10906	ZCUST_SHOW	ZVEH_DROP_OFF
10906	ZCUST_SHOW	RELEASE
10906	ZCUST_SHOW	ZTIME_STARTED
10906	ZVEH_DROP_OFF	ZCUST_SHOW
10906	ZVEH_DROP_OFF	ZVEH_DROP_OFF
10906	ZVEH_DROP_OFF	RELEASE
10906	ZVEH_DROP_OFF	ZTIME_STARTED
10906	RELEASE	ZCUST_SHOW
10906	RELEASE	ZVEH_DROP_OFF
10906	RELEASE	RELEASE
10906	RELEASE	ZTIME_STARTED
10906	ZTIME_STARTED	ZCUST_SHOW
10906	ZTIME_STARTED	ZVEH_DROP_OFF
10906	ZTIME_STARTED	RELEASE
10906	ZTIME_STARTED	ZTIME_STARTED

TABLE 7

Results - Conformance Matrix

Risk	RELEASE	ZCUST_SHOW	ZTECH_SUPP_APPRO	ZTIME_CONTINUED	ZTIME_PAUSED	ZTIME_STARTED	ZVEH_DROP_OFF
RELEASE	44	0	3	4	26	54	
ZCUST_SHOW	44	0	3	3	20	45	
ZTECH_SUPP_APPRO	0	0	0	0	0	0	
ZTIME_CONTINUED	3	3	0	2	7	3	
ZTIME_PAUSED	4	3	0	2	15	4	
ZTIME_STARTED	26	20	0	7	15	25	
ZVEH_DROP_OFF	54	45	0	3	4	25	

FIGURE 2

Results - User Access – Time Analysis

C. Findings – Risk violations (C)

By selecting the relevant user access log for the E2E process, and getting user who has risk, we can filter on related activity included in the risk. As shown in Table 8 - Findings – Risk violations user with ID# “10906” has performed unauthorized two actions listed in SoD as a risk, and when it has been performed. Which needs management’s decisions either to change the authorization or to change the SoD and has approvals for these changes.

TABLE 8

Results - Findings – Risk violations

Service Order Number	Action	Date	Time	User
2120005948	ZCUST_SHOW	01/02/2023	10:00:14 AM	10906
2120005948	ZVEH_DROP_OFF	01/02/2023	10:00:14 AM	10906
2120005950	ZCUST_SHOW	01/02/2023	10:04:10 AM	10906
2120005950	ZVEH_DROP_OFF	01/02/2023	10:04:10 AM	10906
2120005975	ZCUST_SHOW	01/02/2023	10:01:49 AM	10906
2120005975	ZVEH_DROP_OFF	01/02/2023	10:01:49 AM	10906
2120005989	ZCUST_SHOW	01/02/2023	9:55:35 AM	10906
2120005989	ZVEH_DROP_OFF	01/02/2023	9:56:25 AM	10906
2120006010	ZCUST_SHOW	01/02/2023	10:49:04 AM	10906
2120006010	ZVEH_DROP_OFF	01/02/2023	10:49:04 AM	10906
2120006019	ZCUST_SHOW	01/02/2023	8:47:06 AM	10906
2120006019	ZVEH_DROP_OFF	01/02/2023	8:47:06 AM	10906
2120006081	ZCUST_SHOW	01/02/2023	9:58:20 AM	10906
2120006081	ZVEH_DROP_OFF	01/02/2023	9:58:20 AM	10906

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented a novel framework that integrates process mining with automatic reviews to optimize Segregation of Duties (SoD) controls within Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems. Our framework leverages the strengths of both approaches: process mining offers a data-driven, holistic view of ERP processes, while automatic reviews reduce the time of human expertise necessary to identify and assess SoD risks within the specific context of an organization.

The key contributions of this paper are:

- A unified framework for SoD optimization in ERP: We propose a framework that seamlessly combines process mining and manual reviews, enabling a more comprehensive and effective approach to SoD control optimization.
- Process mining for SoD analysis: We demonstrate how process mining techniques can be applied to extract process flows, identify potential SoD violations, and prioritize manual review efforts.
- Human expertise for risk assessment: We emphasize the importance of human expertise in assessing SoD risks identified through process mining.

By implementing this framework, organizations can achieve a more efficient and effective SoD control environment within their ERP systems. The framework can help to:

- **Enhanced Efficiency:** the proposed framework will enhance SoD violation detection, reducing manual review time and effort.
- **Improved Accuracy:** Data-driven insights from role mining complement automatic reviews, leading to more accurate SoD assessments.
- **Continuous Monitoring:** The framework facilitates ongoing monitoring, enabling proactive identification and mitigation of SoD risks. This allows for proactive identification and mitigation of potential violations as user access rights or business processes evolve.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** Combines the benefits of role mining with targeted automatic reviews, to optimize resource allocation.
- **Automated Detection of Violations:** Framework will leverage event logs captured by the ERP system to reconstruct actual process execution. By analyzing these logs, the framework can automatically identify instances where users perform activities that violate pre-defined SoD rules. This significantly reduces the time and resources required for SoD assessments.
- **Data-Driven Insights:** The framework provides data-driven insights into actual user behavior and process execution patterns. This allows for a more objective and comprehensive evaluation of SoD compliance compared to relying solely on static documentation.
- **Identification of Hidden Workflows:** Framework can uncover undocumented process variations and workarounds that traditional reviews might miss. This allows for a more holistic understanding of potential SoD risks within the system.

Future research directions include investigating the application of machine learning techniques to automate aspects of SoD risk assessment and exploring the integration of our framework with continuous control monitoring tools.

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